

iCourts

iCourts Working Paper Series, No. 243, 2021

European constitutional imagination: a Whig interpretation of the process of European integration?

Marco Dani and Agustín José Menéndez

IMAGINE Paper No. 17

Conference EU Constitutional Imagination: Between Ideology and Utopia

iCourts – The Danish National Research Foundation's
Centre of Excellence for International Courts

March 2021

Abstract:

In this essay, we challenge the characterisation of European law as a constitutional order from two related standpoints, namely, the ambiguity of what is meant when characterising European law as constitutional, and the lack of a well-argued narrative explaining how European law became constitutional and what type of constitutionalism it has developed. We start by clarifying the concept and conceptions of constitution, emphasising the centrality of the structural and normative conceptions of constitution. This preliminary conceptual work facilitates the task of elucidating what is exactly being argued when it is claimed that European law is constitutional, and what implications are consequently justified. We then note that while the process of constitutionalisation plays a key role in structuring European law as a discipline, normative reasons underlying such characterisation remain, if anything, more assumed than explicit and fully demonstrated. This leads us to conclude by arguing that may be preferable not to imagine contemporary European law in constitutional terms. At the same time, however, we note that the power effectively held by the European Union reaches so many corners of national legal and socio-economic structures as to render insufficient to merely reject any claim to its constitutionality. The predicament of European Union law is that of a legal order that de facto discharges functional tasks proper of constitutional orders while lacking the requisite democratic and social credentials.

KEYWORDS: European integration, democratic and social constitutional state, constitutional imagination, fundamental constitutional norms

Marco Dani, Associate Professor of Comparative Public Law at the Faculty of Law, University of Trento

Email: marco.dani@unitn.it

Agustín José Menéndez, Profesor Titular of Political Philosophy, Departamento de Filosofía y Sociedad, Universidad Complutense de Madrid

Email: agustmen@ucm.es

IMAGINE has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No 803163).

iCourts is funded by the Danish National Research Foundation Grant no. DNRFF105.

iCourts - Centre of Excellence for International Courts - focuses on the ever-growing role of international courts, their place in a globalizing legal order, and their impact on politics and society at large. To understand these crucial and contemporary interplays of law, politics, and society, iCourts hosts a set of deeply integrated interdisciplinary research projects on the causes and consequences of the proliferation of international courts.

iCourts opened in March 2012. The centre is funded by a large grant from the Danish National Research Foundation (for the period 2012-18).

European constitutional imagination: a Whig interpretation of the process of European integration?

Marco Dani (Università degli Studi di Trento) and Agustín José Menéndez (Universidad Complutense de Madrid)¹

“What is discussed is the tendency in many historians to write on the side of Protestants and Whigs, to praise revolutions provided they have been successful, to emphasise certain principles of progress in the past and to produce a story which is the ratification if not the glorification of the present”
Herbert Butterfield, *The Whig Interpretation of History*, 1931

To Mark Gilbert

In this essay, we challenge the characterisation of European law as a constitutional order from two related standpoints, namely, the ambiguity of what is meant when characterising European law as constitutional, and the lack of a well-argued narrative explaining how European law became constitutional and what type of constitutionalism it has developed. We start by clarifying the concept and conceptions of constitution, emphasising the centrality of the structural and normative conceptions of constitution. This preliminary conceptual work facilitates the task of elucidating what is exactly being argued when it is claimed that European law is constitutional, and what implications are consequently justified. We then note that while the process of constitutionalisation plays a key role in structuring European law as a discipline, normative reasons underlying such characterisation remain, if anything, more assumed than explicit and fully demonstrated. This leads us to conclude by arguing that may be preferable not to imagine contemporary European law in constitutional terms. At the same time, however, we note that the power effectively held by the European Union reaches so many corners of national legal and socio-economic structures as to render insufficient to merely reject any claim to its constitutionality. The predicament of European Union law is that of a legal order that de facto discharges functional tasks proper of constitutional orders while lacking the requisite democratic and social credentials.

¹ The chapter is the product of joint reflections. However, section I was written by Marco Dani; section II and the conclusions by Agustín José Menéndez.

The leitmotiv of this book, the “European constitutional imagination” is part of the progeny of what may be referred as the “constitutional turn” in European studies, most especially on European legal studies. Once regarded as odd,² the characterisation of the European Union as a “constitutional” entity became very frequent in the 1990s,³ and ubiquitous in the early 2000s, to the point that different forms of “Euro-constitutionalism” have become influential theories not only among jurists,⁴ but also political philosophers,⁵ political scientists⁶ and historians.⁷ These “constitutional” theories are deployed as reconstructive tools to account for the development of European law, which would have become a *constitutional legal order* on a par with national democratic legal

²See E. Stein, G. Casper, J.W. Bridge, S.A. Riesenfeld, P.v. Themaat and A. Barav, ‘The Emerging European Constitution’, 72 (1978) *Proceedings of the American Society of International Law*, 166-197, in which Stein starts apologising for the title of the panel: “Professor Stein stated that he must accept blame for the ringing title for the panel. It might strike one as unrealistic and Pollyannaish, if not outright propagandistic in more than one sense” (p. 166).

³ E. Stein, ‘Lawyers, Judges, and the Making of a Transnational Constitution’, 75 (1981) *American Journal of International Law*, 1-27; G. F. Mancini, ‘The Making of a Constitution for Europe’ 26 (1989) *Common Market Law Review*, 595-614.

⁴ See for example J. H. H. Weiler, *The Constitution of Europe, 'Do the New Clothes Have an Emperor?' and Other Essays on European Integration*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1999; A. Von Bogdandy and J. Bast (ed.), *Principles of European Constitutional Law*, Oxford: Hart Publishers, 2009; R. Schutze, *European Constitutional Law*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

⁵ J. Habermas, ‘Remarks on Dieter Grimm's ‘Does Europe Need a Constitution?’’, 1 (1995) *European Law Journal*, 303-307; ‘Why Europe Needs a Constitution’, 11 (2001) *New Left Review*, 5-26; ‘Democracy in Europe, Why the Development of the EU into a Transnational Democracy is Necessary and How it is Possible’ 21 (2015) *European Law Journal*, 546-557.

⁶ S. Hix, and B. Høyland, *The Political System of the European Union*, London: Palgrave, 2011; A. Moravcsik, ‘The European Constitutional Settlement’, 31 (2008) *The World Economy*, 158-83.

⁷ B. Davies, ‘Resistance to European Law and Constitutional Identity in Germany: Herbert Kraus and *Solange* in its Intellectual Context’, 21 (2015) *European Law Journal* 434-459; M. Rasmussen and D S. Martinsen, ‘EU constitutionalisation revisited: Redressing a central assumption in European studies’ 25 (2019) *European Law Journal* 1-22.

orders. The attribution of a constitutional nature to EU law comes to bear when settling concrete legal questions, notably, but not exclusively, conflicts between supranational and national norms regarding the competence of institutions or the substantive content of norms, *entailing* the *supremacy* of European law, its *prevailing* over *any* conflicting national norms, even those belonging to the national, and democratically legitimated, constitution.⁸

In this chapter, we challenge the constitutional readings of European law from two related standpoints, namely, the ambiguity of what is meant when characterising European law as constitutional, and the lack of a well-argued narrative explaining how European law *became* constitutional and what type of constitutionalism it has developed, which propel in our view confused thinking on the relationship between European and national law.

Firstly, theories that characterise European law as constitutional tend to assume that the meaning of constitutional, and consequently the implications of characterising a legal order as constitutional, are (or should be) univocal.⁹ This is hardly the case and tends to give rise to very confused debates, in which implications are drawn from the constitutionality of European law (paradigmatically, its *supremacy* over any other conflicting norm, including national constitutional norms) which would be fully justified only if European law was constitutional in a strong normative sense, but not necessarily in most others. This invites a more articulate analysis of the concept and conceptions of constitution, which we undertake in Section I, so as to be in a position to clarify what is exactly being argued when it is claimed that European law is constitutional, and what implications are consequently justified, and which are not.

Secondly, and quite relatedly, it is clear that whatever the sense in which European law is regarded as constitutional, it *must be* claimed that this results from the *transformation* of an international legal order established through three international treaties into a constitutional order which may define the canonical form of constitutionality in Europe. In other words, given that European Union law was not created as a constitutional order, but rather drafted in the grammar of public international law, anybody claiming that European Union law is *now* a constitutional order must not only specify in what sense this is so, but how European Union law became constitutional. Again,

⁸ See, e.g., Case C-416/10, *Križan and others*, ECLI:EU:C:2013:8.

⁹ This *reductio ad unum* is evident even in the most theoretical analyses, see, e.g., M. Kumm, 'Beyond Golf Clubs and the Judicialization of Politics: Why Europe Has a Constitution Properly So Called' (2006) 54 *American Journal of Comparative Law*, 505-530.

whether such transformation has been completed depends on *what conception of constitution*, and what consequent claims, are at stake. A number of European legal scholars, however, assume that European law has become *constitutional* in a strong normative sense. By doing so, they endorse a *whig legal history of European integration*. Accordingly, the constitutionality of European law is the result of an evolutionary process coherent with the spirit if not the letter of its founding Treaties, in which the consequent transformation of the supranational and the national politics and law were already encrypted.¹⁰ Consequently, the history of European integration would amount to the unavoidable march forward of a specific way of understanding European law and society.¹¹ We note that while the process of *constitutionalisation* plays a key role in structuring European law as a discipline, *normative reasons* underlying such characterisation remain, if anything, more assumed than explicit and fully demonstrated. In fact, the Whig narrative does not only obfuscate the political, social and economic conflicts that come a long way to explain the evolution of European law since its inception, but distract our attention from the recent pattern of evolution of European law, what could be referred as its *neoliberal torsion*. This is why in Section II we revisit the key watersheds in the evolution of European law, and consider how and whether the shifts in the characterisation of European law as a constitutional order were founded and could be justified on the basis of a strong normative conception of constitutionalism. As a result, a less triumphalist and reassuring picture emerges, one in which the legitimacy of European law cannot be taken for granted, in particular if a strong normative conception of constitutionalism is embraced. This leads us to conclude the chapter by putting forward two reasons why it may be preferable not to imagine contemporary European law as a constitutional order. Firstly, we find that Euro-constitutionalism is at best anchored to a *liberal constitutionalism* that may well end up divorcing constitutional law from democratic and social legitimacy, to the extent that it may lead to an authoritarian organisation of power. Secondly, we argue that the European Union lacks the political and social legitimacy necessary to render any normative claim to constitutionality effective, not least because of the growing distance it entertains with constitutionalism in a strong normative sense, at least if the latter is conceived in accordance with the democratic and social constitutionalism at the core of European national post-war constitutions. In that sense, the question

¹⁰ Stein, notes 2 and 3; Weiler, note 4.

¹¹ A. Stone Sweet, 'The Juridical Coup d'État and the Problem of Authority', 8 (2007) *German Law Journal*, 915-928.

is not only whether European law should aim to be constitutional, but whether it *can* be so. At the same time, however, we note that the power effectively held by the European Union reaches so many corners of national legal and socio-economic structures as to render insufficient to merely reject any claim to its constitutionality. The complexity of the predicament of European Union law¹² is that of a legal order that *de facto* discharges functional tasks proper of constitutional orders while lacking the democratic and social credentials to do so.

I. Which constitution, whose constitution?

Many different meanings may be attributed or presupposed in referring to “constitution” or to “constitutional” in a legal or in a political debate. It is indeed accurate to say that “constitution” and “constitutional” are essentially contested concepts.¹³ Or what is the same, how we define them depends on which normative positions we stand for (and viceversa).¹⁴

Debates about European law are not exception as they also reflect the extent to which “constitution”, “constitutional” and “constitutionalism” are normatively, culturally and politically loaded.

To put order in the discussion, it seem to us that it is necessary

- to distinguish, for analytical purposes, five main conceptions of constitution, while stressing that not all of them are placed at the same level of generality, so there are substantive connections between them (subsection 1);
- to add that each conception of constitution raises specific claims to constitutionality, which become extremely relevant in pragmatic legal discourses (subsection 2);
- to conclude that the frequently used (not least in European law debates) concept of “constitutionalism” refers to a specific conception of constitution hearkening back to “liberal constitutionalism”, to be distinguished from “democratic and social constitutionalism” (subsection 3).

¹² Capturing insights from K. Tuori, *European Constitutionalism*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015; but at the same time not disregarding the warnings of P. L. Lindseth, ‘The Perils of “As If” European Constitutionalism’, 22 (2017) *European Law Journal*, 696-718.

¹³ W. B. Gallie, “Essentially Contested Concepts”, 56 (1956) *Proceedings of the Aristotelian Society*, 167–198

¹⁴ See D. Grimm, ‘Types of Constitutions’ in M. Rosenfeld and A. Sajó (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of Comparative Constitutional Law* (OUP, 2013), 98-132.

1. Five conceptions of the constitution

Five are the main conceptions of constitution that are relevant in debates on European law and, in particular, in its relationship with national constitutional norms:¹⁵

1. The *formal* conception of constitution refers to a document or set of documents that *are proclaimed* to contain the fundamental norms governing social interaction and cooperation in a given society.¹⁶ Quite typically, modern legal systems are crowned by one single legal document or a clearly delineated set of documents¹⁷ approved through a special formal procedure established exclusively for that purpose, and which contains quite typically a series of norms establishing and regulating the institutional structure of the polity, and substantive provisions defining the fundamental rules and principles of the legal order (not least fundamental rights).
2. The *functional* conception of constitution refers to the set of norms of social interaction that, regardless of what is formally proclaimed as the constitution, actually *regulate* the fundamental social institutions and practices.¹⁸ It is the sheer centrality of the said norms in the life of the polity that requires us to regard them as constitutional, independently of whether they are written or merely implicit (for example, as “constitutional conventions”), and of the processes through they were elaborated.
3. The *structural* constitution refers to the norms that determine whether other norms are or are not part of a given legal order, and what force and effects they have.¹⁹ The structural constitution plays a fundamental role in founding and sustaining the legal domain; it is not

¹⁵ Other conceptions could be distinguished. Our point is not to be exhaustive, but to draw the distinctions needed to make sense of the debate on European law.

¹⁶ It goes without saying that the standard formal constitution is the *written constitution*. The proclamation of the formal constitution has to be done by institutions (e.g. a constitutional assembly) raising and redeeming a claim to political authority; typically, such political authority is reinforced and higher than that enjoyed by ‘ordinary’ political institutions.

¹⁷ E. Barendt, *Introduction to Constitutional Law*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1998, 26 ff. distinguishes written and codified constitutions, the latter being those in which constitutional norms are included in a single document. See also Grimm note 14, p. 106.

¹⁸ T. Isiksel, *Europe's Functional Constitution. A Theory of Constitutionalism Beyond the State*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016.

¹⁹ H. Kelsen, ‘The Function of a Constitution’, in R. Tur and W. L. Twining, *Essays on Kelsen*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 109-119; part of the characterisation of secondary norms in H.L.A. Hart, *The Concept of Law*, Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1961. Kelsen’s argument makes the validity of the first historical constitution rest on a hypothetical norm (‘the grundnorm’) that has to be presumed if we want to make legal arguments. Implicitly, this seems to us to imply grounding the validity of the constitution on a societal practice, perhaps wider than that hinted at by Hart (who makes judges and lawyers the key and almost exclusive players), as argued by Neil MacCormick in his *Institutions of Law* (Oxford University Press, 2007).

only the *gatekeeper* of legal validity, but is a necessary condition of the functionality of law; in other words, it plays a fundamental role in creating the conditions under which legal norms can be applied by their addressees and by institutions in a more or less coherent fashion.²⁰

- a. It is important to notice that we may speak of the structural constitution in two different senses: a *weak* and a *strong* one.
 - b. When we refer to the constitution of a given legal order in a *weak sense*, we are claiming that we are dealing with a legal order and not merely with a congeries of norms, because from the *standpoint of such legal order itself* (but only from such a standpoint, and not necessarily from others), the validity of its norms is determined by a norm or norms belonging to that very same order.
 - c. But we may also speak of the structural constitution in a *strong* sense. Then, we assume that the norms of that legal order govern the validity of *all* legal norms applicable at the given time and in the given space in which such legal order claims validity, whether those norms are generated or not by that legal order. In this latter sense, the pretence of structural constitutionality goes beyond the legal order itself, and applies to all legal orders and suborders applicable within the space and time in which the legal order is valid. In other words, the strong conception presupposes not only that we are dealing with a legal order, but also with one which claims the last word on the definition of law and legality within a given territory. There are thus close connections between the strong conception of structural constitution and the concept of sovereignty (mediated by concepts such as that of *kompetenz-kompetenz*, not by chance invoked by – some – national constitutional courts when setting limits to the implicit claims to strong structural constitutionality²¹ allegedly raised by the European Court of Justice).²²
4. The *normative* conception of the constitution points to a set of norms characterised by certain normative properties. From a democratic perspective, constitutional norms are those claiming the broadest popular consensus in a particular political community. By contrast, from a cognitivist perspective, constitutional norms are those which reflect the *fundamental* moral values, that is, those values the *correctness* of which can be established independently

²⁰ Quite famously, Kelsen spoke of the “first historic constitution” as containing the structural constitution. Kelsen, note 19, 114 (‘historically first constitution’).

²¹ D. Grimm, ‘Sovereignty in the European Union’, in J. van der Walt and J. Ellsworth (eds.), *Constitutional Sovereignty and Social Solidarity in Europe*, Baden-Baden: Nomos, 2015, 39-54.

²² The European Court of Justice (ECJ) was redenominated Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) after the constitution of the European Union. We hesitated between sticking to one single way of referring to the Court, which would have been simpler, or using one or the other denomination depending on the date of the ruling. We opted for the latter option to avoid a somehow forced and definitely anachronistic use of the terms.

from any procedure of collective decision-making.²³ In both cases, it is the *normative legitimacy* of the norms that justifies their radiating force over the whole legal order, and indeed their capacity to prevail over any other conflicting norm.

5. The *material* conception of the constitution refers to the non-formalised or not fully formalised factors that not only allow to establish the *constitutional normative order*, but also to sustain it over time. Quite typically, the *material conception* assigns a central role to specific constellations of institutional actors (such as political parties).²⁴

The description of these five conceptions of the constitution illuminates the very different senses in which one can make use of the word constitution. However, the mere definition of these different conceptions of the constitution does not clarify in what senses European law can be regarded as a constitutional legal order.

Let us consider this briefly.

Perhaps the only statement that can be made in a rather unqualified manner is that the European Union has a *functional constitution*. It suffices to consider that the basic norms regulating the socio-economic structure and activity, from corporate law to competition law, including decisive elements of labour law are now mostly (but not exclusively) enshrined in supranational law. This can be expressed in a more succinct manner by saying that the legal norms “encoding capital”²⁵ in Europe are mostly part of European Union law.

However, it is far from clear whether the European Union could be said to have a formal constitution. Even if it has become not infrequent to refer to the Treaties (the Treaty on European Union and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union) as *the constitution of the European Union* (at least in the sense that they are regarded as the documents that most closely resemble a written constitution in the supranational legal order), it remains the case that the Treaties

²³ Which normative conception of the constitution is upheld is something that is closely related to the conception of law which one holds. The closer one is to cognitivist conceptions, the more likely it is one supports a non-positivistic conception of law.

²⁴ C. Mortati, *La Costituzione in Senso Materiale*, Milano: Giuffrè, 1940; M. Goldoni and M. A. Wilkinson, ‘The Material Constitution’, 81 (2018) *Modern Law Review*, 567-597.

²⁵ Cf. K. Pistor, *The Code of Capital: How the Law Creates Wealth and Inequality*, Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2019.

are both over and under inclusive: not all fundamental norms are part of them, and at the same time that they contain far too many *non fundamental* legal norms.²⁶

By the same token, it is clear that the European Union has a structural constitution in a *weak sense*. Regulations, directives, the rulings of the Court of Justice and a considerable number of other European norms can be and indeed are regularly *reduced* to a system by reference to a fundamental secondary norm that is part of European Union law itself (much as that is the case not only with national constitutional law, but also with public international law). It is, however, intensely debated whether the European Union has a structural constitution also in a *strong sense*. That would imply that European law, not national law, is the ultimate gatekeeper of legal validity in Europe. That is implicit in the understanding of the structural principles of European Union law (direct effect, supremacy) but has been constantly rejected by national constitutional courts.²⁷ The *contested character* of the claim that Union law has a strong structural constitution is quite related to the question whether the European Union has a *normative constitution*. It seems to us fair to say that while national constitutional actors (notably, constitutional courts) assume that national constitutions remain the normative anchor of law in the European Union due to their democratic and social pedigree, those sustaining the *constitutional character* of European law tend to rely more on *cognitive claims*, based on a certain understanding of the foundational role of *the rule of law* or of the *freedom-enhancing aspect* of subjective economic freedoms. This may reflect different understandings of the *normative constitution* itself, in the terms already pointed above.²⁸

We should add that the distinction of five conceptions of the constitution makes full sense from an analytical perspective. Indeed, the fact that a given set of norms is constitutional in one *sense* does not entail by itself that they are to be regarded as constitutional in any other relevant sense. To viz:

²⁶ It is true that not infrequently, the written constitution does not include all documents of constitutional relevance or salience. This tends to result from the progressive accretion through history to the constitutional canon. In the case of the European Union, however, it is revealing of the fact that the Treaties remain the product of intergovernmental Treaty-making. D. Grimm, 'The Democratic Cost of Constitutionalization: the European Case' (2015) 21 *European Law Journal*, 460-473.

²⁷ Cf. A. Mangia, 'L'interruzione della Grande Opera. Brevi note sul dialogo tra le corti' (2019) *Diritto pubblico comparato ed europeo*, 859-886. See also below at XXYY.

²⁸ The two alternative perspectives are visible respectively in R. Wahl, 'In defence of 'Constitution' and M. Kumm, 'The Best of Times and the Worst of Times. Between Constitutional Triumphalism and Nostalgia' in M. Loughlin and P. Dobner, *The Twilight of Constitutionalism?*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010.

That a given social order is stable, because it has been long tolerated by the population to which it is addressed, does not entail that it is to be regarded as legitimate in a normative sense. By the same token, we should carefully distinguish the claims to weak and strong structural constitutionality: there is a world of difference between the claim that we can identify a fundamental norm around which a legal order is built, and that such fundamental norm governs the validity of all legal norms applicable in a given territory at a given time.

However, neither the different conceptions of the constitution are situated on the same plane of generality nor they stand in splendid isolation from each other, as already emerged when discussing the different conceptions. In that regard, it is important to stress that different claims to constitutionality may enter into conflict. For example, legal and political analysis may lead to the conclusion that the *formal* constitution does not contain the fundamental norms that *de facto* govern social life.²⁹ This urges us to consider what the *functional* and the *material* constitutions reveal about the actual organisation of power in a given society, precisely because the norms that really matter are not enshrined in the formal constitution. This was, for example, the purpose of Ferdinand Lassalle in his essay on the Bismarckian constitution.³⁰ In a similar fashion, we could consider the gap between the formal proclamation of equality and solidarity in contemporary constitutions, and the growing social, economic and existential inequalities which lead to a social practice in which the common action norms being applied are different from formal legal norms. A conflict which can indeed be detected in European Union law too, with perhaps paradigmatic clarity.

Finally, it must be said that how we characterise a given legal order in some dimensions of constitutionality may predetermine our judgment in other dimensions. In that regard, the strong structural and, above all, the normative conceptions of constitutions turn out to be decisive ones, both in themselves and in their relationships with other conceptions of constitution.

To summarise: there is a plurality of *conceptions* of the constitution, and it matters deeply *which specific conception of the constitution* we have in mind when we engage into “constitutional talk”. There are critical differences between affirming that the European Union has a constitution in a normative sense or in a purely functional sense. To put it differently, the polysemic ambivalence

²⁹ Cf. K. Loewenstein, *Political power and the governmental process*, Chicago: Chicago University Press, 1957.

³⁰ F. Lassalle, *Was nun? Zweiter Vortrag über Verfassungswesen*, Zürich: Meyer und Zeller, 1863.

characteristic of the use of the word “constitution” can only be avoided if we clarify *in which sense* we are using the term in each specific case.

2. *Claims to constitutionality in pragmatic legal discourses*

We have already hinted at the fact that each conception of the constitution entails a series of claims regarding the structure and content of the legal order, or in brief, a series of claims to constitutionality. Such claims are relevant in political discourses, but become particularly consequential in legal discourses aiming at settling in an authoritative manner disputes about *how* specific cases should be decided, or indeed *who* should adjudicate upon them. In the latter cases, some of the claims to constitutionality (especially when implying a strong structural conception and the normative conception) may well work as an argumentative *trump card*.

Take for example the recent *Weiss* saga, in which the German Federal Constitutional Court³¹ and the European Court of Justice³² have entered into a rather spectacular conflict. On the one hand, the European Court of Justice found that the quantitative easing programme of the European Central Bank complied with the competence and proportionality requirements of European law, and could thus proceed unimpeded. On the other hand, the final ruling by the judges sitting in Karlsruhe did not only throw serious doubts on its compatibility with German constitutional law, but concluded that such a programme should be invalidated as unconstitutional, and therefore void, if the strong doubts it expressed were to be confirmed. As a result, the *pragmatic* conflict between the two courts (each arguing for a different outcome to the case) is open to be reconstructed as a *conflict between the claims to constitutionality that they made* which results in a conflict concerning the rules to be applied to the concrete case. The ruling of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) implied a claim to the strong structural constitutionality of European law, which excluded a parallel one made on behalf of German constitutional law, and upheld the validity of the decisions taken by the ECB.³³ In its turn, the ruling of the German Constitutional Court advanced a claim to the strong structural constitutionality of German constitutional law, which excluded the one made by the

³¹ BVerfG, Judgment of the Second Senate of 05 May 2020 - 2 BvR 859/15.

³² C-493/17, *Weiss and Others*, EU:C:2018:1000.

³³ A point proven by the press release issued by the ECJ after the *Weiss* ruling of the ECJ. Cf. Press release following the judgment of the German Constitutional Court of 5 May 2020, 8 May 2020, available at <https://curia.europa.eu/jcms/upload/docs/application/pdf/2020-05/cp200058en.pdf>

CJEU on behalf of European law,³⁴ and opened the door to the invalidation of the decisions taken by the ECB. The solution to these conflict between two *incompatible constitutional claims* hinges at the end of the day upon the normative credentials of the conflicting legal orders, as we will see. With this example we have already hinted at the fact that claims to constitutionality can be raised either implicitly or explicitly. It is quite interesting to notice that the German Constitutional Court made its claims to strong structural and normative constitutionality rather explicit, while the CJEU remain quite implicit in its claims, refraining from raising the constitutional card.³⁵ As we will see, the difference between explicit and implicit claims to constitutionality will be highly relevant when reconstructing the legal history of European Community law.

3. Which constitutionalism?

Constitutionalism is a term as ambiguous as constitution. There is a great variety of constitutionalisms, reflecting different political conceptions of the relationship between individual and community, and further complicated by the way in which the relationship between different conceptions of the constitution is understood.³⁶ However, the term tends to be identified (not least, in debates on the law of the European Union) with *liberal constitutionalism*, according to which the fundamental function of constitutional law is to constrain state power, so as to guarantee private autonomy against encroachments by public actors and institutions.³⁷ It is thus a form of *normative*

³⁴ The GFCC seemed to somehow dissolve the conflict between European and national law by also claiming that the ECJ was constructing European law wrongly.

³⁵ When claims to constitutionality are explicit, there is always resort to constitutional language. That is not the case when the claims are merely implicit, in which case there is no need to use the “c” word; it suffices to affirm (or presuppose) that the legal order has the features that correspond to a specific conception of the constitution.

³⁶ See Grimm note 21.

³⁷ A modern rendering in A. Sajó, *Limiting Government: Introduction to Constitutionalism*, Budapest: Central European University Press, 1999. An explicit endorsement of negative constitutionalism, in J.H.H. Weiler, ‘In defence of the status quo: Europe's constitutional Sonderweg’, in J.H.H. Weiler and Marlene Wind (ed.) *European Constitutionalism Beyond the State*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003, 7-24, at 15: “[Our constitutions] are about restricting power, not enlarging it; they protect fundamental rights of the individual”. On its turn, the positive dimension is highlighted by M. García Pelayo, *Las transformaciones del Estado contemporáneo*, Madrid: Alianza, 1977; S. Holmes, *Passions and Constraint: On the Theory of Liberal Democracy*, Chicago: Chicago University Press, 1997; and M. Loughlin, *Political Jurisprudence*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1997.

constitutionalism, which holds that the realisation of the said underlying values is what sustains the legitimacy of the fundamental law.

It is important to keep in mind that *liberal constitutionalism* is an important conception of constitutionalism in historical terms, to the extent that it dominates the history of constitutionalism in Europe in the 19th century, in which the constitution is associated with the *limitation* of public power. Things look different, though, from a historical, comparative or, for that matter, normative perspective. There are good reasons to affirm that the paradigmatic conception of constitution in Europe is the one proper of the democratic and social constitutional state, which makes very different assumptions regarding the relationship between individual, society and state from its liberal counterpart, and emphasises that the constitution constitutes public power, which it both limits and enables, not least with a view to ensure a fundamental degree of *equality* within society.³⁸ This vision, even if only fully realised in Europe in the postwar period, was inspired by interwar constitutional developments, both in Europe and in the US (the New-Deal constitutionalism), which pointed to an activist government capable of contributing to economic growth, coping with market failures and promoting social justice.³⁹

It seems to us that it is of essence to keep in mind that *liberal constitutionalism* is far from being the only possible form of constitutionalism, and that indeed the postwar European “constitutional tradition” endorses *democratic and social*, not *liberal* constitutionalism. To opt for liberal constitutionalism is not only a *normative choice*,⁴⁰ but one that contradicts the identity of contemporary post-war constitutions.

II. The claims to constitutionality of European law: notes for a counter-narrative

In the previous section, the concept of constitution was articulated into five different conceptions, giving rise in turn to distinct claims to the constitutionality of a given legal order. Equipped with these conceptual tools, we revisit briefly the legal history of the European Union. We aim to explore

³⁸ Cf. Maurizio Fioravanti, *Percorsi della storia e tendenze attuali*, Bari: Laterza, 2009.

³⁹ See, e.g., H. Heller, ‘*Rechtstaat* or Dictatorship?’ [1929] (1987) 16 *Economy and Society*, 127-142, G. Dossetti, ‘Funzioni e ordinamento dello stato moderno’ (1953) ‘Quaderni di Iustitia’, 16-39 and García Pelayo, note 37. On New Deal constitutionalism, see B. Ackerman, *We the People, volume II: Transformations*, Cambridge (MA): Harvard University Press, 1998, 256.

⁴⁰ Which, may be said *en passant*, is coherent with the historicist “end of history” and “end of ideology” ideologies.

and assess the genesis of its claims to constitutionality, and in the process, develop the main lines of what could be characterised as a non-Whig constitutional history, one that avoids taking for granted the constitutional character of European law.⁴¹ Instead of a linear unfolding in which the *constitutionality* of European law comes slowly but steadily to the fore, the history of European law is better reconstructed distinguishing several relevant *turning points* in the evolution of European law, not by chance closely connected to wider social, economic, cultural and political transformations, in which the constitutional pretence of the Union becomes increasingly problematic.

We focus on five snapshots capturing as many stages of its evolution by reference to the *specific* claims to constitutionality raised by European institutional actors, most outstandingly the legal services of the European Commission and the judges of the European Court of Justice. We start by analysing the *ambivalence* of the founding Treaties of the European Communities (subsection 1). Then we consider how European institutional actors fashioned European law in distinctive terms from standard international law by presenting it as a new type of legal order characterised by its *autonomy*. This entailed raising a two-folded claim to *structural constitutionality*, in the sense that the claim was *implicitly* to *strong* structural constitutionality (extending to both supranational *and* national law), while *explicitly* it pointed to *weak* structural constitutionality (limited to the sphere of supranational law). Moreover, political and social circumstances (not least, the reinforcement of intergovernmentalism in the wake of the empty chair crisis) ensured that the *implicit claim to strong structural constitutionality* remained merely latent. In the meantime, however, the reach of supranational law expanded, laying the basis for a *claim to functional constitutionality*, which led to a first series of conflicts with national constitutional courts (subsection 2). In the early seventies the circumstances in which European integration evolved changed quite radically. This unleashed functional pressures that encouraged European institutional actors not only to scale up their *implicit and explicit claims to (strong) structural constitutionality*, but also to imbue them with *substantive normative content*. This resulted in a remarkable expansion of the scope of European law and its

⁴¹ We present the turning points in a stylised and sequential fashion. This, by itself, may create the (wrong) impression that there is something *pre-ordained* in the way in which events unfold, that each of them *somehow* naturally leads to the following. This is especially the case when, as here, the dominant narrative intentionally presents facts in such a fashion. But not only there is no such continuity, but it is important to keep in mind that events might have unfolded differently. To make sense of *how European law has evolved*, it is of essence to consider how *it might have evolved*.

recalibration in the light of constitutional principles borrowed from national constitutional traditions (subsection 3). At this point, a range of national institutional actors headed by national constitutional courts engaged into new waves of *resistance* to the pretence of *strong structural* constitutionality of European law. National actors, however, failed to realise the full constitutional implications of the Europeanisation of the *functional constitution* of the socio-economic structure, with obvious repercussions on the actual capacity of national legal orders to claim *strong structural constitutionality* also beyond the policy areas transferred to the European Communities. As a result, the supremacy of the national constitutions became divorced from their actual capacity to shape the substantive content of the legal order, at the very same time that the constitutional equivalence between the supranational and national legal orders was implicitly affirmed and accepted, while leaving open what that entailed in concrete terms (that is, functional, structural or normative equivalence; subsection 4). The financial, economic and fiscal crises that have hit the European Union since 2007 have led to European institutions abandoning most of the self-imposed limits on the claims they made to the constitutionality of the European legal order. This reveals the normative and functional limits that European constitutional theories face (subsection 5).

1. Foundational ambivalences

The establishment of the European Communities in 1951 and 1958 was undertaken through the writing of a new set of legal norms (the Treaties establishing the said Communities),⁴² which, in their turn, foresaw the production of a whole raft of additional norms through which the objectives set in the Treaties were to be spelled out (in particular, decisions in the case of the ECSC⁴³ and regulations and directives in the case of the EEC and the Euratom⁴⁴).

As a result, there were good reasons to assume that a new legal order had been created, an order which would soon be referred as “Community law”. This implied, by itself, a claim to the *weak structural constitutionality* of this new legal order (alongside a claim to *functional constitutionality*,

⁴² The three founding Treaties (of the Coal and Steel Community of 1951, of the European Economic Community of 1957, of EUROATOM of 1957) together with the Merger Treaty of 1965, through which the three independent communities (and legal orders) were fused into one.

⁴³ Cf. Article 14 of the ECSC Treaty.

⁴⁴ Cf. Article 189 of the EEC Treaty; Article 161 of the Euratom Treaty.

if only because key elements of the economic order were regulated or affected by Community norms).

But whether there were other *constitutional claims to be made* remained unclear because of the *ambivalence* of the founding documents of this new legal order, an ambivalence which was not least the result of the ratification failure of the closely interrelated Defence and Political Treaties in 1954. The failure of these initiatives, which aimed at establishing an autonomous supranational political level of government and pointed to modelling European law in the semblance of federal constitutional law, was however followed by the negotiation and ratification of the Treaty Establishing the European Economic Community, and of that establishing the European Atomic Energy Community (Euratom), which could be seen as pointing to a radically alternative way of creating a framework for cross-border relations and interactions, or as an indirect and oblique way of realising the goals enshrined in the unratified Treaties.

As a result, the trio of European Treaties was open to be interpreted in at least two different ways:

- The *form* of the documents in which the key set of new norms were contained and regulated seemed to point to Community norms being part of a (sub)system of international law. After all, the Communities were established through (three) documents negotiated in diplomatic conferences and written with the grammar and syntax of international Treaties. This would have entailed that each national legal order would determine the actual force of Community norms according to its own constitutional norms, as was the case with “classical” international norms.⁴⁵ Consequently, the only claim to constitutionality inherent in the treaties was one to *weak* structural constitutionality.
- At the same time, however, not only the goals set in the Treaties, but also the *institutional structure* was also infrequent in *classical* international Treaties.⁴⁶ This emerged in the range of powers and competences assigned to the European Communities. In particular, it was slightly idiosyncratic that the Treaties delineated procedures through which Community institutions could produce new norms (what would come to be known as secondary norms), not least with a view to harmonise national legal norms (ex article 3h TEC).

There were thus some reasons which supported characterising European law as a form of international law adventuring in governance and policy-making, and for this purpose aspiring to

⁴⁵ As indeed argued by AG Roemer in his conclusions to Case 26/62, *Van Gend en Loos*, ECLI:EU:C:1962:42.

⁴⁶ B. De Witte, ‘The European Union as an international legal experiment’ in G. De Búrca and J. H. H. Weiler, *The Worlds of European Constitutionalism*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012, 25.

something more than a claim to *weak structural constitutionality*.⁴⁷ A similar ambition would have been supported by a *cognitivist normative* claim to constitutionality (perhaps based on the degree to which European integration contributed to peace and prosperity),⁴⁸ and would have entailed claims to formal and, in due course, to functional constitutionality.

This tension between form and substance (but also between political intentions and functional needs) reflected the underlying disagreements between the very actors that played a key role in the drafting and implementation of the Treaties. In particular, the same individuals⁴⁹ that favoured deeper integration (not least, the Political Treaty of 1952)⁵⁰ and who had contributed to formulate the norms which seemed to differentiate Community law from international law into the three founding Treaties, were to a large extent to be the same that promoted at a later stage the interpretation of Community law as if it was *something else* than a “classical” international legal order, on the basis of which several additional claims to constitutionality could be raised (and indeed, as we will see, were raised).

2. An Autonomous Legal Order: a claim to strong structural constitutionality on hold

The foundational ambivalence of the founding Treaties morphed into constitutional ambiguity in the first two decades of European integration. What was at stake at the time was whether European law was to be construed as an international legal order or not. To break from the mould of international law in which the Treaties had been framed, it was argued that European law constituted a radically new type of legal order, and that it was characterised by its autonomy (subsection A). This theoretical formulation was given canonical form in several rulings of the European Court of

⁴⁷ J. H. H. Weiler, ‘The Geology of International Law – Governance, Democracy and Legitimacy’ (2004) 64 *German Yearbook of International Law*, 559-561.

⁴⁸ As later hinted at by the ECJ in *Van Gend* and as summarised by P. Pescatore ‘La constitution, son contenu, son utilité. La constitution nationale et les exigences découlant du droit international et du droit de l’intégration européenne: Essai sur la légitimité des structures supra-étatiques’, (1992) 111 *Zeitschrift für Schweizerisches Recht* 41-72.

⁴⁹ Paradigmatic in this regard are the figures of Michel Gaudet and Pierre Pescatore. See A. Boerger and M. Rasmussen, ‘The Making of European Law: Exploring the life and work of Michel Gaudet’, (2017) 57 *American Journal of Legal History*, 51-82. P. Pescatore, ‘Les travaux du “groupe juridique” dans la négociation des traités de Rome’, (1981) *Studia diplomatica*, 159-178.

⁵⁰ R. T. Griffiths, *Europe's First Constitution: The European Political Community, 1952-1954*, London: Kogan Page, 2000.

Justice, albeit it must be stressed that the latter reflected the debates of a broader set of actors. The result was the creation of the theoretical space in which it was possible to raise a dual claim to constitutionality. Explicitly, the Luxembourg judges were very careful, and limited themselves to raise *claims* to weak structural constitutionality, fully confined to the European legal order. Yet lurking behind the affirmation of the direct effect and the primacy of European law over conflicting national norms in *Van Gend* and *Costa* was a much stronger claim to constitutionality, to *strong structural constitutionality* (subsection B). At any rate, Community law developed for years as a complement, not an alternative, to national constitutional orders (themselves in the process of being reshaped by reference to democratic and social constitutionalism), acquiring a consistency and relevance that supported claims to *functional* constitutionality, owing to the increasing importance of cross-border economic activities (subsection C). The growing salience of Community law, alongside the tensions at the core of the *dual claim to constitutionality* raised by European institutional actors, paved the way to the first wave of resistance of national institutional actors (subsection D).

A. An autonomous legal order?

Once the Treaties were in force, and even more so, once they started to be implemented, it was just a matter of time that conflicts would arise between supranational law and national law. This prompted the question of how such conflicts were to be solved, and consequently, how the relationship between European law and national law was to be structured.

The first thing to be observed is that at this stage references to the *constitutionality* of European law were marginal. With very few exceptions, neither institutional actors nor scholars dared to raise explicit claims to the constitutionality of European law when discussing how to decide the first conflicts between national and supranational law.⁵¹ This in itself is telling, given the present tendency to see the history of European integration as the realisation of the constitutional nature of Community law, without problematising the ubiquity of constitutional language and rhetoric. When no justification is offered of how an international order was transformed into a constitutional order,

⁵¹ The exception was constituted by E. Stein, 'Toward Supremacy of Treaty-Constitution by Judicial Fiat: On the Margin of the Costa Case', (1965) *Michigan Law Review* 491-518; see also the allegations of the Italian barrister that represented Mr Costa before the ECJ: A. Arena, 'From an Unpaid Electricity Bill to the Primacy of EU Law: Gian Galeazzo Stendardi and the Making of Costa v. ENEL', (1989) 30 *European Journal of International Law*, 1017-1037.

it might be concluded that it is assumed that the said order was, in one sense or the other, constitutional since its inception. A claim that is not only wrong in substantive terms, but also contradicted by the fact that “constitutional talk” about European Community law would only emerge in the late seventies and early eighties, as will be shown below.

Indeed, it seems to us it would be clarifying to reflect on why barely any legal scholar sustained the constitutional nature of European Community law in the fifties and sixties. Considering that several of the actors who played a key role in the relevant debates had entertained the idea that some form of European law could play a central role in the building of some kind of “United States of Europe”, certainly the cause was not lack of political commitment or insufficient legal imagination. It seems to us that two factors were decisive:

Firstly, the establishment of the European Communities as a polity with a full-blown democratic normative constitution had been attempted—and had failed. The rejection of the Defence Treaty by the French Parliament on August 1954 entailed the demise of the European Political Community Treaty, which was a blend of international Treaty and embryonic democratic normative constitution.⁵² As a result, the failure of this Treaty precluded the usage of constitutional lexicon. Secondly, and most decisively, the reconstruction of Western European nation-states after the Second World War revolved around a strong *normative* conception of democratic and social constitutionalism, which came to define constitution and constitutionalism *tout court*. This was most obviously in France and in Italy, where two “revolutionary” democratic constitutions were written.⁵³ But the close association between constitutional law and the highest democratic legitimacy permeated the conception of the constitution even in countries where there was no *new* constitutional beginning after the war (such as Belgium, the Netherlands or Luxembourg).⁵⁴ Or what is the same, the social and economic transformations of the 40s, 50s and 60s left their mark in the conception of the constitution to such an extent that it would have been inaccurate to characterise as constitutional the legal order of the European Communities, which had been established through a *diplomatic, inter-governmental* agreement, and which did not correspond to

⁵² Griffiths, note 50.

⁵³ See B. Ackerman, *Revolutionary Constitutions: Charismatic Leadership and the Rule of law*, Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2019, chapters 4, 5, 7 and 8.

⁵⁴ Cf. T. Judt, *Postwar*, New York: Allen Lane, 2005; M. Conway, *Western Europe's Democratic Age*, Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2020.

the *characteristic template* of the constitutions of mass-democratic polities.⁵⁵ Indeed, the democratic legitimacy of the European Communities was *entirely* derivative, more akin to that of a supranational administrative structure than that of a full-blown political system.⁵⁶ Consequently, talk about “constitution” and “constitutional” applied to Community law seemed at best premature.⁵⁷

Under such circumstances, even supporters of a federal Europe in which federal law would make a claim to structural and normative constitutionality in a strong sense had to accept that the only realistic goal was a much more modest one, namely, to succeed in establishing that Community law was not “mere” international law, if possible in such a way as to prepare the ground for later claims to constitutionality other than in a weak structural sense to be made. This is what was achieved through the depiction of European law as a *new* and *autonomous* legal order, which stood *separate and equal* in its relation to national legal orders, and *distinct* from public international law.

The originality of Community law created the theoretical and practical space in which it was possible to deny the international character of Community law, at the very least according to the more “traditional” paradigm of international law, while preparing the ground for later bolder claims to constitutionality. In particular, the “newness” of Community law came hand in hand with the characterisation of the relationship between European law and national law in terms of “autonomy”. In negative terms, this implied a rejection of the outright subordination of Community law to national law, as would have been the case if Community law would qualify as standard public international law. In positive terms, the two orders were identified as separate but equal. In such a way, a claim was made to something more than a weak structural constitutionality which was at the same time tamed by the profession of “separation” between the two legal orders, not least reflected the acceptance of the attributed character of the powers of the Communities, limited to cross-border trade, plus a limited set of flanking policies, crucially agricultural policy and transport.⁵⁸ The autonomy of European law was thus the product of calculated ambivalence.

⁵⁵ Indeed, not by chance, the German 1949 Fundamental Law, which was the result of a process in which US occupying authorities played a fundamental role, was not labelled as a constitution, but indeed as a fundamental law.

⁵⁶ E. Forsthoff, *Der Staat der Industriegesellschaft: dargestellt am Beispiel der Bundesrepublik Deutschland*, C. H. Beck, 1971.

⁵⁷ P. Lindseth, *Power and Legitimacy*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010.

⁵⁸ See below II.2.B.

B. The canonical formulation of autonomy: A dual claim to structural constitutionality

As legal historians have clearly shown, the characterisation of Community law as a new and autonomous legal order was the fruit of a collective work undertaken by institutional actors, scholars and practitioners.⁵⁹ However, “autonomy” was given canonical form in the foundational rulings of the European Court of Justice (ECJ), particularly in the *Van Gend en Loos* and *Costa* cases.⁶⁰

It is to be noticed that the ECJ settled the cases by reference to categories central to international law. Thus, direct effect was but an alternative way of referring to the self-executing character of a Treaty provision.⁶¹ At the same time, however, the Court shaped these categories in a way that enabled their strategic reconceptualisation, by affirming that Community law did not only govern the question of what force was to be acknowledged to Community norms by Community institutions (as would have been the case if applying the template of international law with its companion weak claim to structural constitutionality), but also by national institutions (something which pointed to something more than a weak claim to structural constitutionality).⁶²

Still, as has already been advanced, the success of the autonomy narrative is closely related to its (calculated) ambiguity, stemming from the tension (if not contradiction) between what was implicitly argued, and what was explicitly said, resulting in an ambiguous claim to constitutionality, or rather, in the advance of two different claims to constitutionality once and at the same time.

⁵⁹ Cf. M. Rasmussen, ‘The Legal History of the European Union: Building a European Constitution’, in *Oxford Research Encyclopedia: Politics*, 2020, available at DOI:10.1093/acrefore/9780190228637.013.106.

⁶⁰ While there is a clear tendency to regard the two cases as instances through which the ECJ applied a single coherent vision of Community law, a close reading of the judgments reveals the extent to which “Euro-constitutionalism” was work in progress. Consider the following. In *Van Gend*, the Court characterizes Community law as a “new order of international law”, while in *Costa* the reference to the international law is dropped, Community law being now characterised as a “new legal order” without any further qualification.

⁶¹ Cf. B. de Witte, ‘Retour à « Costa » -La primauté du droit communautaire à la lumière du droit international’, (1984) *Revue trimestrielle de droit européen* 1984,425-454; ‘Direct Effect, Primacy and the Nature of the Legal Order’ in G. de Búrca and P. P. Craig (eds.), *The Evolution of EU Law*, 2nd ed, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2011, 323-362. See also O. Spiermann, ‘The Other Side of the Story : An Unpopular Essay on the Making of the European Community Legal Order’ (1999) 10 *European Journal of International Law*, 763-89.

⁶² *Ibidem*.

On the one hand, *Van Gend* and *Costa* pointed to a very innovative characterisation of the terms of relationship between Community law and national legal orders. In particular, direct effect and primacy were capable of becoming the bridges through which Community norms could penetrate into each and every legal national order, if only because the norm establishing the effect of Community norms was to be regarded as part and parcel of both Community law and each and every national legal order. This entailed the beginning of a process of *fusion* of the two legal orders, and implied a claim to structural constitutionality other than a weak one.

On the other hand, the explicit constitutional claim being raised by the ECJ remained rather self-restrained:⁶³

Firstly, both rulings were drafted in an ambivalent language, which combined symbolic rupture (reflected in the reference to “a new legal order”, or in the affirmation that individuals had a key role in the process of integration) and marked orthodoxy (very clear in the resort to the categories of international law, not least direct effect) which seemed to reassure national higher courts that not much had actually changed.

Secondly, the actual consequences of the rulings were very limited. The revenue at stake in *Van Gend* was relatively modest, because the decision only affected the interpretation of transitory norms, while the Italian government won the day in *Costa*, as the Luxembourg judges recognised the European validity of the (politically decisive) nationalisation of electricity in Italy.

Thirdly, and critically, the ambivalent claim to structural constitutionality came hand in hand with the assumption that there was a clear division of labour and competences between supranational and national law.⁶⁴ Community law was defined as a legal order having an impact on the way in which states treated (mainly) goods and workers in cross-border movement, and which reinforced the overall design of each national socio-economic structure (as was the case with coal and steel restructurings and common agricultural policy).⁶⁵ Not by chance, the fundamental substantive

⁶³ M. Cappelletti, ‘Is the European Court of Justice “running wild”?’ (1987) 12 *European Law Review* 3-17.

⁶⁴ See for example the main lines of ‘The Brussels Report on the General Common Market’, Luxembourg: Information Service of the High Authority of the European Coal and Steel Community, 1956, available at http://aei.pitt.edu/995/1/Spaak_report.pdf. See also A. Milward, *The European Rescue of the Nation-State*, London: Routledge, 1994.

⁶⁵ S. Giubboni, *Social Rights and Market Freedom in the European Constitution. A Labour Law Perspective*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2009.

provisions defining the core objective of the Treaty establishing the European Community, the internal market, imposed formal, not substantive, obligations on Member States, through the prohibition of discrimination on the basis of nationality. In other words, Member States were precluded from closing their economic borders and from treating goods and workers from other Member States in ways dissimilar to those they applied to their own goods and workers. But Member states remained free not only to determine the substantive content of their regulations, but also to make substantive choices concerning their socio-economic policy. Consequently, building an internal market did not entail eliminating economic borders, but rather rendering them predictably porous, sufficiently open so as to allow goods and workers to flow across them. But if that was so, then the direct effect and supremacy of Community law could be regarded as entailing constraints concerning cross-border movement, not affecting the core of the legal order of each Member State. Consequently, the *separateness* of the two legal orders basically was intended as meaning that European law was the legal order of cross-border trade, which further complemented national legal orders by means of creating the conditions for their further realisation⁶⁶ The implicit premise underpinning such characterisation was that it was possible to distinguish quite clearly the sphere of Community law from that in which national legal orders were applicable.

It should also be kept in mind that the transformative capacity of European law was still very limited in 1964. Community norms were not only limited in number then, but any additional norm added to what would soon start to be called *acquis communautaire* had to be unanimously agreed within the Council of Ministers. Moreover, the political environment in the mid and late sixties further contributed to reinforce the national control of European integration.⁶⁷ As is very well-known, these were the years in which the Communities took a clearly intergovernmental direction, not least, albeit not exclusively, because of the way in which the “empty chair” conflict was solved in 1966 through the so-called Luxembourg compromise.⁶⁸ For all these reasons, the Member States retained the power to contain the growth of the supranational legal order.

⁶⁶ That was the way, we would insist, in which common policies such as agricultural policy were conceived. That is the view underpinning Milward, note 64.

⁶⁷ The combination of legal supranationalism and political intergovernmentalism was theorised in J. H. H. Weiler, ‘The Community System: the Dual Character of Supranationalism’, 1 (1981) *Yearbook of European Law*, 267-306.

⁶⁸ On the empty chair crisis, M. Gilbert, *European Integration*, Lanham: Rowman and Littlefield, 2012, pp.77ff.

The gift of autonomy was its *duplicity*. At the very same time that the claim to strong structural constitutionality was ventilated, it was tamed and put on hold by means of (re)separating the two legal orders. As a result, Community law was made into a legal cloth sufficiently dissimilar to international law and sufficiently similar to national law as to affirm a basic degree of functional even if not normative equivalence between the two legal orders. In such a way the subordination of Community law to national law, implicit in any theory that grants ultimate primacy to national, whether labelled dualistic or monistic, could be *de facto* transcended.

C. Community law as complement to democratic and social constitutionalism

As the programme of the creation of an “embedded” internal market⁶⁹ was progressively realised under the conditions described in the previous subsection, the substantive affinities between Community law and national democratic and social states seemed to become more marked. Firstly, supranational law complemented national Democratic and Social States. Community norms, as we saw, mainly were applied to cross-border relationships which national legal orders could not effectively regulate. Not by chance, a key holder of Community rights in the period was the cross-border worker, who became entitled to the same socio-economic rights as national workers, thus contributing to define communities of social insurance on the basis of residence, not nationality.⁷⁰ Secondly, Community law was largely respectful of the substantive choices enshrined in national constitutions. As was pointed in the previous subsection, most of the obligations imposed by Community law were formal ones, leaving substantive choices in the hands of each Member State. At the same time, European integration contributed to economic growth by stabilising the conditions under which cross-border trade in goods proceeded, something that rendered possible to fund the consolidation of social states⁷¹.

⁶⁹ J. G. Ruggie, ‘International Regimes, Transactions, and Change: Embedded Liberalism in the Postwar Economic Order’, (1982) 36 *International Organization*, 379-415.

⁷⁰ The emergence of a community of social insurance on the basis of residence was articulated in Regulation (EEC) No 1612/68 of the Council of 15 October 1968 on freedom of movement for workers within the Community, *OJL 257, of 19.10.1968, pp. 2–12*.

⁷¹ Something that led to a faster growth of intra-Community trade than international trade of the Member States of the Communities. Cf. Milward, note 64, pp. 167ff.

Thirdly, European law was substantially defined by reference to national legal orders, and, at the end of the day, by the *collective of national constitutions*. This is paradigmatically reflected in the way in which the European Court of Justice defined in 1970 the unwritten principle of protection of fundamental rights by reference to the constitutional traditions common to the Member States.⁷² In less grandiose terms, the derivative character of European law was reflected in the use of comparative arguments when interpreting and applying European law, not least by the legal services of the different European institutions.⁷³ This was so even if the degree of substantive convergence between national legal orders was strong only at the level of abstract principles, while there were major differences in terms of how such principles were institutionalised and operationalised. That rendered unavoidable that the number and intensity of conflicts would grow as integration became closer, and the concrete divergence between national legal systems increased in successive waves of enlargement of the Communities.

What should be stressed now is that the primacy stemming from *Costa* was a muted one because Community law developed as a complement to national constitutional orders, a complement which was moreover largely homogeneous in substantive terms with them. By the same token, at this stage of the evolution of European law, the production of secondary law was quite limited, and remained the product of unanimous decision-making within the Council, something which also favoured complementarity.

The more that supranational law thickened through the adoption of regulations and directives realising the programme of economic integration, the more there was a case to raise a claim to functional constitutionality of Community law. That may come some way to explain why the German Constitutional Court used the “c” word to refer to Community law already in 1967,⁷⁴

⁷² Case 29/69, *Stauder*, ECLI:EU:C:1969:57; Case 11/70, *Internationale*, ECLI:EU:C:1970:114.

⁷³ See, for example, Koen Lenaerts, ‘Interlocking Legal Orders in the European Union and Comparative Law’, (2003) 52 *International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, 873-906.

⁷⁴ 22 BVerfGE 293: “The EEC Treaty is in a sense the constitution of this Community. The legal provisions enacted by the Community organs within their Treaty powers, the ‘secondary Community law’, constitute a separate legal order, the norms of which are neither international law nor national law of the Member States. Community law and the domestic law of Member States are ‘two autonomous legal orders, different from each other’; the law created by the EEC Treaty derives from an ‘autonomous source of law’”.

admittedly limiting itself to concede what was uncontroversial, once it was recognised that Community norms formed a distinctive legal order, or what is the same, once the soundness of a weak claim to structural constitutionality on behalf of supranational law is accepted.

D. The first wave of national constitutional resistance

Even if ambivalent and muted, the claim to structural constitutionality was bound to result in theoretical (constitutional) unrest as European law expanded, that is, as the number of regulations and directives increased and their remit widened. The substantive intertwining of the national and supranational legal orders, reflected in the synthetic conception of “constitutional traditions common to Member States” put forward in *Internationale*⁷⁵ and *Stauder*,⁷⁶ was aimed at quelling such unrest. In particular, some national constitutional courts (chief among them the German and the Italian ones) took seriously the doubts which were emerging in lower courts regarding the mismatch between the ambiguous claims to structural constitutionality made by supranational actors and the lack on the side of Community law of the procedural and substantive features proper of a democratic and social constitutional order. By placing the unwritten principle of fundamental rights protection (and consequently the collective of national constitutions) at the very basis of Community law, the Court of Justice was seen (and rightly so) as pre-empting attacks on the *primacy* of European law.⁷⁷ Still, what started as a revolt of guardians of constitutionality would then spread to other jurisdictions and to other kinds of courts.⁷⁸ The tension will only ease after a peculiar reformulation, on the side of national courts, of what the autonomy of European law entailed, something which was only possible by neglecting the extent to which what was labelled as “economic law” had massive constitutional implications, as we will see in Section 3.A.⁷⁹

⁷⁵ Case 11/70, *Internationale Handelsgesellschaft*, ECLI:EU:C:1970:114.

⁷⁶ Case 29/69, *Erich Stauder v City of Ulm – Sozialamt*, ECLI:EU:C:1969:57.

⁷⁷ J. H. H. Weiler, ‘The Transformation of Europe’, (1991) 100 *Yale Law Journal*, 2403-2483.

⁷⁸ Such as the decision of the French Conseil d’État in *Cohn-Bendit*, 22 December 1978, 11604. A general panorama in A. Hofmann, Resistance against the Court of Justice of the European Union (2018) 14 *International Journal of Law in Context*, 258-74.

⁷⁹ Italian Constitutional Court, *Frontini*, ruling 183/1973, of 18 December 1973.

3. From an autonomous to a constitutional-like legal order

In the late seventies and early eighties, we can observe three decisive transformations that represent a clear break in the evolution of Community law, and that by themselves prove the wrongness of reconstructing its history in a *whig* key. Firstly, national constitutional actors came to accept the claim to autonomy of Community law raised by supranational actors, trying in the process to give it a peculiar twist (Subsection A). At the same time, secondly, changes in supranational policy led to a decisive transformation of the substantive content of Community law, which implicitly entailed a redefinition of its substantive scope; this set Community law into a potential collision course with national legal orders (Subsection B). Thirdly, European institutional actors made stronger the explicit claims to structural constitutionality, in the process reinforcing the claims to functional and normative constitutionality. In particular, the CJEU started to make use of constitutional language, and reshaped the scope of the claim to primacy over conflicting national laws, making it explicit that it could extend to national constitutional norms (Subsection C).

A. National acceptance of the claim to autonomy of Community law

As was pointed in section 2.D, national courts, and very especially national constitutional courts, had resisted, on democratic procedural⁸⁰ and on substantive⁸¹ grounds, the claim to *autonomy* of Community law put forward by European institutional actors.

This backlash resulted in inter-institutional declarations and new lines of case law through which the explicit features of Community law were restyled, coming to resemble more closely the characteristics of a constitutional order.⁸² In 1976, the Act establishing the direct election of the Members of the European Parliament was finally agreed, putting an end to the secondment of national parliamentarians. The political core of a new supranational citizenship seemed to be emerging, further developing the “proto-citizenship” latent in the personal status as developed by the European legislator (and fine-tuned by the ECJ in the sixties and seventies).⁸³ Moreover, a series of supranational fundamental rights emerged, one case at a time, from new lines of case law of the Luxembourg court, inspired by the collective of national constitutions and by the European

⁸⁰ Italian Constitutional Court, judgment n. 14/1964, 7 March 1964.

⁸¹ See *Frontini*, note 79 and German Federal Constitutional Court, *Solange I*, BVerfGE 37, 271 [1974] CMLR 540.

⁸² E.g. B. Davies, *Resisting the European Court of Justice*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2012, chapter 5.

⁸³ A. J. Menéndez and E. D. H. Olsen, *Challenging European Citizenship*, London: Palgrave, 2020.

Convention of Human Rights (which was precisely at the time becoming of age as the Strasbourg Court came of age).⁸⁴

As a result of the above mentioned transformations, the stance of some of the key guardians of national constitutionality became more nuanced. On the one hand, both the Italian and the German Constitutional Courts subscribed to the “separate but equal” doctrine on the basis of the axiological equivalence between supranational and national law. As long as European law kept on developing its original project (the legal order of cross-border activities, to which human rights were being progressively uploaded), the said courts would not engage into any form of review of the contents of European norms, and could indeed accept both the direct effect and the primacy of European norms.⁸⁵ On the other hand, however, the national constitutional courts maintained unaltered their claims to the *supremacy* of national constitutions. This entailed that the *primacy* of Community law was not self-standing, but rested upon the national constitutional decision to open itself to supranational law. This was reinforced by the role national constitutional courts assumed as guardians of the core of the fundamental values of national constitutions in the process of European integration.

The result was a counterclaim to the implicit supranational claim to strong structural constitutionality on the side of the CJEU. Indeed, the *controlimiti* doctrine⁸⁶ served firstly and foremostly to prevent any claim to *sovereignty* of the European Communities, that is, to rule out any capacity of the European Communities to set their own competence basis and, consequently, impose their normative claims.

The shift operated by national constitutional courts was not by chance contemporary to the diffusion of legal theories that constructed Community law on a constitutional key. The eighties were the years in which Eric Stein ceased being the odd man out labelling Community law as a constitutional

⁸⁴ G. de Búrca, ‘The Evolution of EU Human Rights Law’, in Craig and de Búrca, note 61, pp. 465–97.

⁸⁵ Italian Constitutional Court, ruling 170/84, *Granital*, 5 June 1984 ; German Federal Constitutional Court, *Solange II*, (22 October 1986) BVerfGE 73, 339, [1987] 3 CMLR 225.

⁸⁶ On the “contro-limiti” doctrine, see for example P. Faraguna, *Ai confini della costituzione: Principi supremi e identità costituzionale*, Milan: Franco Angeli, 2015, 74-75, 84-88. A useful contribution is R. Nevola, ‘Le limitazioni della sovranità statale in favore dell’Unione europea nella giurisprudenza costituzionale’, Roma: Corte Costituzionale, 2014, available at https://www.cortecostituzionale.it/documenti/convegni_seminari/STU_262.pdf.

order and became the scholar that opened a new path in the analysis of European law,⁸⁷ not least explored by the “integration through law” project led by Mauro Cappelletti.⁸⁸ The paradox, as we will see, is that both constitutional courts and scholars were proceeding on the assumption (or faith) that the substantive content of European law was becoming akin to that of national constitutions, precisely at the time at which European law was in flux, being radically transformed by what we suggested labelling its *neoliberal torsion*.⁸⁹

B. The substantive transformation of Community Law

The demise of the international monetary order in 1971 (the so-called Bretton Woods system) and the economic crisis triggered in 1973 by a rapid rise in the price of oil unleashed a period of financial and economic turbulence, during which the socio-economic consensus which had slowly emerged and during the post-war years was put to trial and found inadequate. Despite the extent to which states (some with more conviction than others) tried to make use of the monetary and fiscal levers to reflate economies, both stagnation and inflation set in.⁹⁰ This created the conditions under which neoliberal socio-economic views, which had been marginal all through the post-war period, could be imposed with full force.⁹¹

The substantive consistency and breadth of Community law was radically reshaped in this new socio-economic context. Two developments were crucial.

Firstly, a European monetary infrastructure (the European Monetary System, EMS) was (re)created by the end of 1978. This intergovernmental arrangement not only prioritised the fight against inflation over other socio-economic goals, such as full employment or distributive justice, but consolidated the hegemonic role played by the only independent European central bank, the

⁸⁷ Stein, above, note 3.

⁸⁸ M. Cappelletti, M. Seccombe and J. H. H. Weiler, *Integration through law*, 5 volumes, Berlin: De Gruyter, 1985-1988.

⁸⁹ E. Mostacci, ‘La sindrome di Francoforte: crisi del debito, costituzione finanziaria europea e torsioni del costituzionalismo democratico’ (2013) *Politica del diritto*, 481-558.

⁹⁰ Overviews in A. Glyn, P. Armstrong and J. Harrison, *Capitalism Since World War II: The Making and Breakup of the Great Boom*, London: Fontana, 1984; B. Eichengreen, *The European Economy since 1945: Coordinated Capitalism and Beyond*, Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2007.

⁹¹ A. Glyn, *Capitalism Unleashed: Finance, Globalization, and Welfare*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2007; P. Ther, *Europe since 1989: A History*, Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2016.

Bundesbank, which *de facto* was granted the power to set monetary policy of the EMS as a whole.⁹² As a result, the political space for autonomous national monetary (and even fiscal) policies was drastically reduced, contrary to what had been the case in the precedent monetary infrastructures of the European Payments Union and Bretton Woods.

Secondly, almost at the same time, the legal services of the Commission and the Court of Justice favoured a new interpretation of free movement of goods, no longer to be understood as an operationalisation of the principle of non-discrimination on the basis of nationality, but as a concretisation of the right to private property and of entrepreneurial freedom, which required eliminating (in principle) all obstacles to its exercise.⁹³

In both cases, we observe not only a shift in substantive content, but also in the very scope of Community law. As for the EMS, the fight against inflation required to turn such goal into a pre-condition for all socio-economic policies. In other words, monetary stability was to be not only the objective of monetary policy, but aspired to be a mandatory condition to be fulfilled before other goals could be pursued through fiscal or social policies. As for free movement of goods (and later all other economic freedoms), it became a yardstick to gauge the validity of all national regulatory measures, and not only those affecting cross-border trade.

Consequently, Community law ceased being a neutral constraint on domestic policy choices, and instead became loaded in favour of a neoliberal socio-economic model with private property and entrepreneurial freedom at its centre, aspiring to exert their substantive influence over the whole breadth and scope of national legal orders.

This was immediately constructed by the Commission as entailing the emancipation of economic integration from intergovernmental political consensus, in the process rendering corporate actors into its main drivers through the judicial vindication of their economic freedoms.⁹⁴

Again, however, the full potential of these trailblazing changes would not be drawn fully yet. The EMS was a powerful *vincolo esterno*, but it was still possible to introduce negotiated changes in the

⁹² J. Leaman, *The Bundesbank Myth. Towards a Critique of Central Bank Independence*, Houndsmill: Palgrave, 2001, 181ff, 193ff.

⁹³ Case 120/78, *Cassis de Dijon*, ECLI:EU:C:1979:42.

⁹⁴ ‘Communication from the Commission concerning the consequences of the judgment given by the Court of Justice on 20 February 1979 in case 120/78 (“Cassis de Dijon”)’, *OJ C 256, of 3.10.1980, pp. 2–3*.

parities of the currencies.⁹⁵ By the same token, the new understanding of Community rights was for the time being limited to free movement of goods, while *de jure*, even if increasingly less *de facto*, remnants of the embeddedness of capital remained in place. Things started to change in 1987, with the Single European Act, and even more with its natural corollary, Directive 88/361 on free movement of capital,⁹⁶ which confirmed and radicalised the shift implicit in *Cassis de Dijon*. Still, as was pointed out, the Court treaded a cautious path, and was rather self-restrained in its case law until the signature of the Maastricht Treaty.

What we find important to stress at this juncture is that the EMS and the case law following *Cassis de Dijon* pointed to a radically transformed relationship between European law and national law. Before 1979, the claim to strong material constitutionality implicit in primacy was somehow softened by the purely formal and thus relative character of the obligations stemming from Community law (non-discrimination on the basis of nationality). After 1979, the actual implications of the claim to primacy were critically changed by the new substantive characterisation of the obligations stemming from the European monetary infrastructure, the new conception of free movement of goods, and by the implicit claim to full-range scope of Community law.

One of the reasons why this was not fully realised at the time (and to a large extent, keeps on not being realised) was that the European Communities occupied the European imaginary by borrowing the language of democratic and social constitutionalism at the same time that the institutions embarked on a policy agenda that would undermine the very constitutional commitments it pretended to emulate at the supranational level.

C. From implicit to explicit constitutional language

Not by chance, the transformations in the substantive content and scope described in the previous subsection came hand in hand with a change in the way in which European institutional actors raised claims to the constitutionality of European law. Firstly, the implicit claim to strong structural

⁹⁵ Several devaluations were agreed between 1979 and 1987; however, the amount by which the D-Mark was revalued did not compensate the full amount of “real” depreciation of such currency. See A. Graziani, *Lo sviluppo dell’economia italiana*, Torino: Bollati Boringhieri, 2001, pp. 133, 137. The rigidification of changes after 1987 played a key role in the collapse of the EMS in 1992.

⁹⁶ Council Directive 88/361/EEC of 24 June 1988 for the implementation of Article 67 of the Treaty, *OJL 178*, 8.7.1988, p. 5–18.

constitutionality was emboldened. In particular, from *Simmenthal II* onwards the language of *primacy* was replaced by that of *supremacy*, with a quite unequivocal reference to European law prevailing over national constitutional norms.⁹⁷ Secondly, explicit reference to the constitutional character of Community law was made in *Les Verts*.⁹⁸ The “c” word was finally pronounced, scaling up the muted claim in *Costa*, namely that European law was not only “separate and equal” vis-à-vis national law, but was also of the same normative fabric as national law, i.e. a “constitutional” legal order. This partially reflected the rise of the constitutional narrative in legal scholarship, and at the same time, nourished it on what concerned European law.

D. European Union law unleashed: One money in one market

European law was in a process of radical and rapid mutation since the late seventies (in the terms that we described in subsection B). The Treaty of Maastricht would consolidate the neoliberal socio-economic turn (confirmed by a deeply asymmetric economic and monetary union), while fostering the further wrapping of the constitutional restyling (reflected for example in the relabelling of the European personal status increasingly focused on mobility as “European citizenship”). This determined that supranational constitutionalism came to resemble even more liberal constitutionalism while diverging from democratic and social constitutionalism.⁹⁹

In the fateful wake of the collapse of the Berlin Wall and of German (first monetary, then political) reunification, European leaders agreed on an unprecedented form of monetary union, which would result in the creation of a new and peculiar common currency.

On the one hand, the monetary side of EMU certified that the German government held the stronger hand. Monetary policy was federalised and its implementation entrusted to a radically independent central bank, which was left to define the monetary rules concretising its originally narrow mandate.¹⁰⁰

⁹⁷ Case C-106/77, *Amministrazione delle finanze dello Stato v SpA Simmenthal*, ECLI:EU:C:1978:49.

⁹⁸ Case C-294/83, *Les Verts*, ECLI:EU:C:1986:166.

⁹⁹ D. Grimm, *The Constitution of European Democracy*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017, page highlights the (excessive) robustness of the discipline of economic freedoms on European law, which contrasts with the weak democratic legitimacy credentials of European law.

¹⁰⁰ Governing Council of the ECB, *A stability-oriented monetary policy strategy for the ESCB*, 13 October 1998, available at https://www.ecb.europa.eu/press/pr/date/1998/html/pr981013_1.en.html; Governing Council of the ECB,

On the other hand, political consensus on the introduction of a common currency did not extend to an agreement on how to reconcile the singleness of the new monetary policy with the plurality of national fiscal policies. The euro was planned to be a currency without a supporting state. Coordination of national fiscal policies was not to be entrusted with a political centre, the assumption being instead that a sufficient degree of direction would largely result from the enforcement of fiscal rules erecting walls of separation among national exchequers,¹⁰¹ and setting ceilings to both the levels of annual deficits and the total stock of public debt.¹⁰² Finally, the freedom of capital owners was dramatically enlarged, by means of extending its sphere of application to flows originating or ending in third countries,¹⁰³ in a move that was deliberately intended to empower financial markets to act as forces disciplining national fiscal choices. In the wake of the ratification of the Maastricht Treaty, the European Court of Justice extended to all economic freedoms the characterisation of free movement of goods that it had put forward in *Cassis de Dijon*.¹⁰⁴ At the very same time, the Luxembourg judges developed a case law which increased the bite of the principle of non-distorted competition as yardstick of review for the validity of large swathes of national norms.¹⁰⁵ By 1995, the European Court of Justice, in tandem with the Commission, had *de facto* become a peculiar form of constitutional court, reviewing national norms in the light of constitutional standards that, despite the abundant constitutional rhetoric, continued to diverge from those employed in national constitutional quarters.

The ECB's Monetary Policy Strategy, 8 May 2003, available at https://www.ecb.europa.eu/press/pr/date/2003/html/pr030508_2.en.html.

¹⁰¹ As results from Articles 101 TEC (now Article 123 TFEU) and 103 TEC (now Article 125 TFEU), as amended by the Maastricht Treaty.

¹⁰² Article 1 of the Protocol to the Maastricht Treaty on the Excessive Deficit Procedure.

¹⁰³ By virtue of Article 56 TEC, as amended by the Maastricht Treaty (now Article 63 TFEU).

¹⁰⁴ Cf. Case C-55/94, *Gebhard*, ECLI:EU:C:1995:411; Case C-415/93, *Bosman*, ECLI:EU:C:1995:463; Joint Cases C-163/94, C-165/94 y C-250/94, *Sanz de Lera*, ECLI:EU:C:1995:451.

¹⁰⁵ From the mid 80s, the ECJ started to make use of competition provisions to engage into a strict scrutiny of state actions shaping the socio-economic structure. Cf. Case C-18/88, *Régie des télégraphes*, ECLI:EU:C:1991:474; Case C-41/90, *Höfner and Elser*, ECLI:EU:C:1991:161; Case C-387/92, *Banco Exterior de España*, ECLI:EU:C:1994:100; Case C-206/06 *Essent*, ECLI:EU:C:2008:413; Joined Cases C-399 and 401/10 *Bouygues*, ECLI:EU:C:2013:175. Cf. the prescient F. Snyder, 'Ideologies of Competition in European Community Law', (1989) 52 *The Modern Law Review*, 149-78.

This changed the pace of the transformation of the substantive content of European law which had started in 1979. If in *Costa* the collective good had justified the expropriation of electricity, and in *Internationale* the establishment and running of a common agricultural policy had been found to uphold conspicuous constraints on the right to private property, by 2007 the Court would find that the right to strike was to be trumped by freedom of establishment. Or, to be more precise, the right to strike had to be exercised in such a way as not to undermine the right to freedom of establishment, another way of taking the democratic “risk” out of the right to strike.¹⁰⁶

It is important to stress, indeed, that the exterior form and the interpretative techniques of democratic and social constitutionalism were placed at the service of a modified form of supranational liberal constitutionalism, in which the trio of private property, entrepreneurial freedom and monetary stability came to be defining the substantive bases of the legal order. In other words, behind provisions with a similar wording to those enshrined in national democratic constitutions, lied a radical substantive break resulting from the prioritisation of private property and entrepreneurial freedom and the corresponding downgrading of other socio-economic objectives.

The salience of these transformations accounts for a second but very ambiguous wave of resistance on the side of national constitutional courts, to which we turn in the next section. The tensions, however, will only come fully to the surface in the aftermath of the European crises. From 2008 onwards, functional pressures (not least to avoid the uncontrolled unravelling of the Eurozone) led to the radicalisation of the claims to constitutionality made by supranational institutions, a development that would push on an ever more precarious terrain the legitimacy and stability of European law.

4. A second wave of national constitutional resistance: failing to take seriously the constitutional nature of economic law

The ratification of the Maastricht Treaty paved the way to a second wave of resistance to the constitutional claims made by European institutional actors, following the steps of the first wave in

¹⁰⁶ Even more invasive and abrasive was the ruling in Case C-314/08, *Filipiak*, ECLI:EU:C:2009:719, in which the ECJ found that the decision of the Polish Constitutional Court to limit the temporal effects on one of its own rulings undermined the effectiveness of the primacy of Union law, and was, consequently, to be declared in breach of European law itself.

the seventies (section 2 D). If objections were raised at the time of the ratification of the Treaty on European Union in the first half of the 1990s, they became even more acute after the codification in the treaties of the principle of respect of the national identities of Member States.¹⁰⁷

National constitutional courts, led by the German Constitutional Court, seemed to render more robust the *controlimiti* by means of developing new grounds on which they would be inclined to review the constitutionality of European norms. In its *Maastricht* ruling,¹⁰⁸ the guardian of German constitutionality strengthened the principle of attribution as a yardstick to measure the German constitutionality of European norms and decisions. In 2009, in its *Lisbon* ruling,¹⁰⁹ the judges sitting at Karlsruhe added a new head of review, (national) constitutional identity, and beefed up the competence review, by drawing more stringent limits regarding the Europeanisation of a number of competences. However, it must be added that the new review powers were later gummed, as the Court ruled out intervening unless breaches were not egregious (in more technical terms, “structural”).¹¹⁰

What national courts seemed keen on preserving was not so much the supremacy of the Constitution in procedural and/or substantive terms, but the very kernel of sovereignty, the competence over the delimitation of competences (or *kompetenz-kompetenz*) and, as a reflection, their own power as guardians of that sovereignty. All attempts at making that slightly more substantial (as through the drawing of “red lines” to the powers to be held by the European Union) failed to take into account the necessary consequences of their previous jurisprudence, which had enabled the Union neoliberal drive. Suffice in that regard to remind the reader of the ratification of the Maastricht Treaty leading to a dramatic change in the German Basic Law, namely, the constitutionalisation of the independence of the central bank, which so far had been guaranteed only by an act of Parliament.¹¹¹ On the basis of such an amendment, the Federal Constitutional Court carved out a sphere of public power (monetary policy, defined in opposition to economic policy),

¹⁰⁷ Cf. Article F of the Maastricht Treaty, now article 4(2) TEU.

¹⁰⁸ BVerfG, Judgment of 12 October 1993 - 2 BvR 2134/92, 2 BvR 2159/92.

¹⁰⁹ BVerfG, Judgment of the Second Senate of 30 June 2009 - 2 BvE 2/08.

¹¹⁰ BVerfG, Order of the Second Senate of 06 July 2010 - 2 BvR 2661/06.

¹¹¹ Article 88 of the German Fundamental Law. See C. Joerges, ‘What is Left of the European Economic Constitution?’, *Working Paper, EUI LAW, 2004/13*, available at <https://cadmus.eui.eu/bitstream/handle/1814/2828/law04-13.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>.

no longer subject to parliamentary democratic control. In the process, also the functional constitution of the European Union was radically changed, making of monetary stability a sort of meta-principle steering the direction of other EU policies.

5. The ultimate gambit: redefining national constitutionalism in the image of European Union law

From 2007, the European Union, and very especially the Eurozone, were hit by overlapping yet distinctive financial, economic and fiscal crises, triggering scores of punctual decisions and structural reforms aimed at their containment and overcoming.¹¹²

Functional reasons (summarised in the ambivalent rallying call to “save the Euro”) led to remarkable changes in the organisation of power in Europe, deeply affecting the terms of relationship between supranational law and national law. In particular, the supranational level of government was assigned more powers to discipline and control the way in which member states defined their fiscal, labour, tax and social policies. Social expenditure and social rights became the only macroeconomic adjustment variables left in the hands of Member States,¹¹³ forced to undertake painful internal devaluations given the sheer impossibility of resorting to an external devaluation. In such a context, freedom of movement ended up becoming a peculiar functional substitute of social policy, given that migration to the Eurozone core emerged as the only alternative to destitution open to a good number of the young in the Eurozone periphery. The result was a regression towards a form of liberal constitutionalism, fragmenting and pulverising public power in the name of preserving the rights of individuals and, notably, private property and entrepreneurial freedom.

The implicit and explicit claims to strong material constitutionality of EU law were further strengthened. To the point that the relationship between European law and national law was to a considerable extent reversed, with European law posing as the template which national legal orders should follow.¹¹⁴ This can be chiefly appreciated in the field of fiscal rules. The legally and constitutionally peculiar Fiscal Compact requires the Member States to patriate into their

¹¹² A. J. Menéndez, ‘A European Union in Constitutional Mutation?’, (2014) 20 *European Law Journal*, 127-41.

¹¹³ F. Costamagna, ‘National social spaces as adjustment variables in the EMU: A critical legal appraisal’, (2018) 24 *European Law Journal*, 163-90.

¹¹⁴ A. Somek, ‘Delegation and Authority: Authoritarian Liberalism Today’ (2015) 21 *European Law Journal*, 340-360.

constitutional system the fiscal rule limiting the volume of annual deficits.¹¹⁵ At the same time, the CJEU has been empowered to control the extent to which national reforms to that effect comply with this obligation.¹¹⁶ An equally remarkable development concerns the procedures of surveillance of national compliance with fiscal rules. In the name of reducing political discretion, the power to impose sanctions is now assigned jointly to the Commission and a *minority* of Member States, or what is the same, sanctions could be applied despite a majority (below a qualified one) objects to them.

The crises have also revealed the normative and functional limits of the claims to the structural and normative constitutionality of European law on the side of European institutions. The European Union has been proven unable to redeem such claims because it lacks the necessary preconditions for doing so. Not even at the height of the crisis has the European Union been capable of exercising sovereign public power in an explicit fashion. The European Union can act as a *vincolo esterno* (exerting *negative powers*), but not as an autonomous political actor (making use of *positive powers*). It lacks the institutional, the material and, above all, the legitimacy resources to do so, to a considerable extent because its functional and material constitutions are far apart from the ones presupposed by democratic and social constitutionalism.¹¹⁷ This is true of all European institutions, including those which, as the ECB, not only have seen their powers expanded during the crises, but have played a central role in its governing. It is true that the so-called “unconventional” monetary policies of the ECB were decisive in the denouement of the crises, whichever is the assessment we make of their opportunity and effectiveness. But it is telling that the ECB could only act in a decisive manner by pretending that it was merely discharging its modest role of implementing monetary policy in a fully rule-based manner.¹¹⁸ Only by means of cloaking its political role as

¹¹⁵ Treaty on Stability, Coordination and Governance in the Economic and Monetary Union, article 3(2).

¹¹⁶ *Ibidem*, article 8(1).

¹¹⁷ Grimm, note 99, makes the argument focusing on the European Parliament, but it can be projected to the European Union as a whole. The same line of reasoning was already present in F. Scharpf, *Governing in Europe: Effective and Democratic?* Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2000.

¹¹⁸ As argued repeatedly by the ECB, not least in the judicial sagas of *Gauweiler* and *Weiss*.

purely technical could the ECB take the decisions it took. Had the ECB fully disclosed the nature of what it was doing, its authority would have been immediately depleted.¹¹⁹

III. Conclusions

The combination of the analytical tools put forward in Section I and the historical reconstruction contained in Section II reveals that “Euro-constitutionalism” makes two central claims to the constitutionality of European Union law: a claim to strong structural constitutionality, which is hard to disentangle from a claim to sovereignty on behalf of the European Union, and a claim to normative constitutionality, which is grounded on liberal constitutionalism, in particular, on private property, entrepreneurial freedom, monetary and financial stability as overriding principles of European law.¹²⁰

The claim to strong structural constitutionality cannot be fully redeemed by the European Union due both to normative and functional reasons. As we saw in section II.5, contradictions at the core of the asymmetric economic and monetary union have put European institutions under strong functional pressure to come very close to claim that European Union law is the constitutional order of a fully sovereign polity. This neglects that the EU does not have, and is unlikely to acquire any time soon, the capacity to act as a constitutional sovereign.¹²¹ The constitutional umbilical cord with national constitutions and national institutional structures cannot be severed.

However, it would be too rash by half to conclude that the strong claim to structural constitutionality is as a result simply irrelevant. A claim to strong structural constitutionality on behalf of European law, even if incapable of being legally and politically redeemed, does contribute to the enervation of national public power. This is indeed the path that the European Union has trodden in the last three decades. Power, very especially on what concerns socio-economic issues, has shifted away from national parliaments and governments, but it has not been recreated in an equivalent form at the European level, with the result of being dispersed to the benefit of some

¹¹⁹ It suffices to consider what would have been the outcome of the *Weiss* saga had the ECB explicitly admitted to the exercise of fiscal powers.

¹²⁰ A. J. Menéndez, ‘A European Union founded on capital?: The fundamental norms organising public power in the European Union’, in C. Jouin (eds.), *La Constitution Matérielle de l’Europe*, Paris: Pedone, 2019, 147-66.

¹²¹ D. Chalmers, ‘European Restatements of Sovereignty’ in R. Rawling, P. Leyland and A. Young, *Sovereignty and the Law: Domestic, European and International Perspectives*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013, 186-212.

private actors and technocratic (or pseudotechnocratic¹²²) bodies. In other words, the power of European institutions is not so much positive, to shape policy, as negative, to constrain and discipline the policy choices taken by others.

The second claim, that to normative constitutionality, implies a frontal attack on the democratic and social constitutionalism. The fact of the matter is that the force characteristic of democratic constitution-making and/or democratic constitutionalisation has not manifested itself at the supranational level. There has been neither a European constitutional moment nor the fundamental norms organising power in the EU have been appropriated by political actors with a view to develop a constitutional ethos, or for that matter, have evolved into a democratically supported constitution. In such circumstances, imagining European law *as if* it was constitutional entails the risk of divorcing constitutional law from its democratic and social basis. Something that unavoidably paves the way to an authoritarian regression.¹²³

On such a basis, it is simply impossible to claim that acknowledging to European law the condition of “constitutional order” is either a neutral way of referring to the object of study of a legal-dogmatic discipline, or a means of promoting the transformation of European law in the semblance of democratic and social constitutionalism.

The perverse way in which European lawyers “imagined” European constitutionalism has resulted in an updated version of liberal constitutionalism, only wrapped up in the rhetoric of its historical opponent and replacement. The result is not so much legal dogmatics, as dangerous legal mythology.

What is needed, however, is not a mere rejection of the constitutional character of European law, because European integration has proceeded in such a way that a good deal of the powers transferred to the supranational level have major constitutional implications. The constitutional implications of European integration and of Europeanisation have to be fully taken into account without devaluing the currency of the democratic and social constitution. Therefore, the European constitutional imagination has to rely, first and foremost, on the collective of national democratic and social constitutions.

¹²² P. Krugman, ‘Crisis of the Eurocrats’ *New York Times*, May 22, 2014.

¹²³ H. Heller, ‘Authoritarian Liberalism?’, (2015) 21 *European Law Journal*, 295-301; M. A. Wilkinson, Authoritarian Liberalism in the European Constitutional Imagination: Second Time as Farce?, (2015) 21 *European Law Journal*, 313-339; W. Streeck, ‘Heller, Schmitt and the Euro’, (2015) 21 *European Law Journal*, 361-370.

Author(s): Marco Dani & Agustín José Menéndez
Title: European constitutional imagination: a Whig interpretation of the process of European integration?
iCourts Working Paper Series, No. 243, 2021

Publication date: 18/March/2021

URL: <http://jura.ku.dk/icourts/working-papers/>

© Author
iCourts Working Paper Series
ISSN: 2246-4891

Marco Dani, Associate Professor of Comparative Public Law at the Faculty of Law, University of Trento
Email: marco.dani@unitn.it

Agustín José Menéndez, Profesor Titular of Political Philosophy, Departamento de Filosofía y Sociedad, Universidad Complutense de Madrid
Email: agustmen@ucm.es

The iCourts Online Working Paper Series publishes pre-print manuscripts on international courts, their role in a globalising legal order, and their impact on politics and society and takes an explicit interdisciplinary perspective.

Papers are available at <http://jura.ku.dk/icourts/>

iCourts
- The Danish National Research Foundation's Centre of Excellence for International Courts
The Faculty of Law
University of Copenhagen
Karen Blixens Plads 16
2300 Copenhagen S
E-mail: icourts@jur.ku.dk
Tel. +45 35 32 26 26